

Library Standards in Practice: A Bibliometric Perspective

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Abstract

Library standards refer to guidelines that outline ideal staffing levels, funding, collection size, organization, services, and spaces for libraries. The study aims to examine the evolution of the research landscape on library standards globally, focusing on growth trends and mapping through bibliometric techniques. The study collected 382 documents from the Scopus database, using the various keywords (standards OR guidelines OR regulations OR rules OR practices) and ("Academic library" OR "Public library" OR "Medical library" OR "Special library" OR "National Library") as titles. This study executes the scientific knowledge mapping, visualizing the relationships between different perceptions and ideas within the library standards. Its finding reveals a significant growth in library standards. The 'Journal of Academic Librarianship' was the most productive, while the USA contributed the most publications. Most of the multi-authored publications were produced in these periods, whereas the article was the most published document. The network map expresses traditional and emerging research areas in library Standards, demonstrating interdisciplinary linkages and evolving priorities of digital Standards. The investigation of the global landscape highlights extensive engagement, the importance of connectivity, and the progression of research paradigms. This comprehensive analysis directs forthcoming inquiries towards deeper insights.

Keywords: Library Standards, Bibliometrics, Library Guidelines, Library Best Practices.

Introduction

Standards are essential instruments that ensure consistency, quality, and interoperability across various domains, including social, religious, technical, and educational sectors. In some cases, standards function similarly to laws as legally enforced, while others are upheld by tradition, common sense, or mutual agreement (St. Clair, 1974). They are vital in reducing chaos, promoting organizational credibility, and fostering individual creativity, even though conflicts

may arise when different standards serve divergent area-specific (Tomer, C 1992). The standards-making process itself contributes to establishing order, enhancing efficiency, and facilitating interoperability.

The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) defines a standard as a documented guideline, specification, or criterion developed to ensure consistency, quality, safety, and interoperability in products, services, or processes. These standards are formulated by international bodies, industry organizations, or governments to encourage best practices and operational compatibility. Similarly, the British Standards Institution (BSI) characterizes a standard as a repeatable and agreed-upon method of doing something, codified into precise technical documents that reflect the input of producers, sellers, users, regulators, and other stakeholders. Both institutions say standards simplify life and improve reliability by embedding expert consensus into practice.

Standards are crucial for ensuring operational quality and efficiency in the library and information science realm. It provides a consistent framework for cataloguing, classification, metadata, and various processes across different Libraries (Oguche, 2023). Standards establish the guidelines and best practices that govern various housekeeping operations of library management, including cataloguing, classification, digital resource management, preservation, and user services. These standards are developed by reaching a consensus among the experts in the specific area groups. Standards-making bodies include the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), the Library of Congress, the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA), and the National Information Standards Organization (NISO). In India, the BIS (Bureau of Indian Standards) works as part of the ISO at the national level to develop and distribute standards to the entire country.

Bibliometric Analysis of Library Standards

This study used bibliometric analysis, a quantitative statistical method, to systematically analyze research trends and evolutions of research areas. (Pham-Duc et al., 2020).

Examining production patterns, trends, and the influence of publications will help assess the organization of the growth of research literature, which makes it easier to explore a variety of topics and disciplines (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). It encourages bibliometric analysis to gain traction quickly across various study areas. Several indicators are frequently utilized in data analysis, including the total number of publications, the most cited texts, the co-occurrence network, factorial analysis, and thematic evolution. This study assessed the scientific environment of Standards, Rules, Regulations, Practices, or Guidelines within a Library, whether it is a Public, Academic, or Special Library. It also aids in understanding how standards are discussed and implemented in various types of libraries, whether public, academic, or special, and provides a systematic method to explore research themes and institutional contributions in this vital area.

Background and Previous Studies

The concept of library standards has evolved to address both qualitative and quantitative aspects of library operations. These standards are essential for aligning library resources with user needs, supporting academic goals, and adapting to technological advancements. Focusing on qualitative as well as quantitative library standards Roalfe W.R. (1949) emphasizes the necessity of revising law library standards to enhance their effectiveness in legal education. It underscores the importance of aligning library resources with student needs to ensure optimal utilization. The role of law librarians is highlighted as essential in the development and implementation of these standards. Furthermore, library management is presented as a critical professional responsibility rather than a routine administrative duty. Ultimately, he advocates for law libraries that are well-resourced, student-centered, and adaptable to evolving educational requirements. Building on this perspective, Jadhav et al. (2012) evaluate the existing status of Veterinary College Libraries in India by applying the prevailing standards of the Academic Veterinary Medical Library, USA. They evaluate the result report on the Library Building and adequacy of Space, financial resources and provisions, status of qualified library professionals, and library services rendered to the users by Veterinary colleges in India. And found that the Veterinary libraries in India are at an infant stage. Any planning can be easily adopted and implemented in the initial stage, and therefore, the Veterinary libraries can be developed on modern lines to suit the changing needs of users and technological developments, so that investments will be less and the output efficiency will be optimum to meet the organizational goals. Similarly, Tarabula et al. (2023) have studied the 2022 Standards for Hospital Libraries, developed by the Medical Library Association (MLA), which reflect the evolving needs of healthcare environments and the role of librarians in supporting medical professionals. These standards emphasize diversity, equity, and inclusion, advocating for the broader term “health sciences library” to encompass the roles beyond physicians, such as nurses and pharmacists. The standards also stress the need for librarians to engage with technology, ensuring library resources are integrated into electronic health records and accessible remotely. This document serves as a benchmark for hospital libraries, guiding them in maintaining continuous access to evidence-based resources and adapting to the dynamic healthcare landscape.

In the context of national frameworks, Obille, K. L. B. (2007) evaluates library standards issued by various agencies in the Philippines. The study reveals that most standards predominantly emphasize inputs such as collections, staffing, infrastructure, and services while offering limited attention to service efficiency and optimal resource utilization. Moreover, the standards issued by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) vary in terms of native user requirements, collection sizes, and clarity, indicating a need for more consistent and outcome-focused guidelines.

Focusing on India, Rathinasabapathy (2014) has studied the available library standards and regulations, particularly in light of technological transformations. The integration of digital

environments has significantly changed core operations like acquisition, processing, circulation, and serials management, highlighting the inadequacy of traditional benchmarks. As a result, recent updates have amended guidelines regarding library infrastructure, furnishings, and resources. The study underscores the key role of regulatory bodies like the University Grants Commission (UGC), which leads reforms by forming expert committees of Library and Information Science professionals. He advocates for the implementation of compulsory standards for newly established institutions seeking accreditation, thereby ensuring the delivery of high-quality library and information services. Similarly, Ncube et al., (2022) examine the challenges modern academic libraries face in developing countries, particularly due to technological advancements and operational hurdles. They emphasize the potential of the digital landscape to enhance decision-making and efficiency while noting the lack of planning and stakeholder involvement. The study highlights the need for mutual understanding and effective communication among patrons, service providers, and library staff. They recommend adopting automation, international benchmarking practices, and revising regulatory frameworks to improve services and infrastructure.

Focusing on reform and suggestions.

The development and implementation of library standards remain a crucial concern, particularly within academic and professional library settings. Building upon the need for structured and inclusive guidelines Narang & Kumar Vishwakarma, (2021) emphasize the urgent need for inclusive standards for academic medical libraries in India. They argue that sufficient infrastructure, digital resources, and technology investments are vital to meet user demands and support institutional growth. They also stress the need for policymakers and educators to participate actively in updating recruitment policies, addressing staff shortages, and modernizing library facilities. Additionally, they call for a strict regulatory framework, urging the National Medical Commission (NMC) to implement quality indicators aligned with premier institutions like IITs and IIMs. In the same way, Lakshmi, (2003) explores the standards available for evaluating college libraries in India, comparing the recommendations made by the University Grants Commission (UGC) with those from professional organizations like ACRL and CoFHE. Her analysis reveals that no officially revised and approved standards exist for Indian college libraries. She proposes a model set of standards that includes components such as a preamble, objectives, management, finance, staffing, access, information resources, organization, services, computerization, networking, infrastructure, working hours, and maintenance. Naik (2021) focuses on information and communication-based international standards used in Library and Information Science to manage, process, and disseminate services effectively. He categorizes these into five categories as bibliographic and data management system standards, metadata standards, information processing and retrieval standards, web technology standards, and network standards. These frameworks enable professionals to streamline library operations efficiently. At the Institutional level, Khademizadeh & Farajpahlou, (2019) assessed the libraries of Shahid Chamran University of Ahvaz using Iranian university library standards. They report a significant decline in the compliance rate of the Faculty of Literature and Humanities Library

from 88% in 2004 to 45% in 2018 due to relocation issues, collection mishandling, and a termite infestation. Centralizing faculty libraries between 2007 and 2010 was intended to optimize resources but instead disrupted tracking systems. While adopting a web-based library management system improved certain operations, it also revealed gaps due to staff's limited technological skills. The study calls for updated acquisition and cataloguing policies, improved data documentation, expansion of academically aligned collections, and preservation of institutional knowledge through experienced librarians.

Objectives of the study

1. To determine the annual growth of publications related to library standards;
2. To find out the most productive authors and authorship patterns;
3. To visualize the most frequently used keywords and trending topics of library standards;
4. To identify the most cited and referenced publications of library standards;
5. To identify the most influential Articles related to library standards.

Methodology

The bibliographic data about scientific production are taken from the Scopus database, which provides comprehensive bibliographic datasets covering various aspects of scholarly communications that have high utility for bibliometric analysis. So, we collect the data from it by using the string TITLE (standards OR guidelines OR regulations OR rules OR practices) AND TITLE ("Academic library" OR "Public library" OR "Medical library" OR "Special library" OR "National Library"). A total of 382 records were exported from the Scopus database till 2024. Further calculations were conducted to derive key indicators, which have been systematically tabulated and presented in this paper. These indicators have also been utilized for graph plotting and analysis.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

After extracting the data, it was subsequently tabulated, examined, and analyzed using various bibliographic indicators to make intended observations. Table 1 reveals a broad overview of the dataset from 1879 to 2024, including 382 documents with an annual growth rate of 0.48%. The average age of these documents is 13.1 years, and they receive an average of 6.929 citations each, totaling 10,966 references. The dataset includes 466 keywords plus 837 authors' keywords, with 683 authors contributing, of which 151 documents are single-authored. Collaboration metrics indicate an average of 1.96 co-authors per document and a low international co-authorship percentage of 4.974%. The document types are predominantly articles (304), followed by a few books, book chapters, conference papers, editorials, and errata. This analysis highlights the dataset's key bibliometric characteristics and trends, providing valuable insights into the research landscape over the timespan.

Table 1: Bibliometric Summary of Scholarly Output (1879-2024)

Description	Results
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	163
Documents	382
Annual Growth Rate %	0.48
Document Average Age	13.1
Average citations per doc	6.929
References	10966
DOCUMENT CONTENTS	
Keywords Plus (ID)	466
Author's Keywords (DE)	837
AUTHORS	
Authors	683
Authors of single-authored docs	151
AUTHORS COLLABORATION	
Single-authored docs	158
Co-Authors per Doc	1.96
International co-authorships %	4.974
DOCUMENT TYPES	
Article	304
Book	4
book chapter	12
conference paper	19
editorial	2
erratum	2

Annual Scientific Production

In Figure 1, we saw that from 1879 to 1962, there was minimal activity, with only occasional articles appearing in the 1960s and 1970s. A slow but steady increase began in the 1980s and 1990s, with annual publications gradually rising to four by 1990. The early 2000s saw moderate growth, surpassing 10 articles yearly after 2007. A rapid surge occurred from 2010 onward, with annual counts exceeding 14 articles and reaching a peak of 31 in 2020. Since then, publication numbers have remained consistently high, averaging around 24-26 articles annually. This sustained output indicates a strong and stable research trend, highlighting a significant expansion in document production over time. The forecast suggests continued growth, potentially surpassing 50 publications annually in the future, indicating an expanding research landscape.

Figure 1: Production of the Document over the period

Ranking of LIS Journals by Scholarly Output and Citations Performance

Table 2 evaluates the journal's impact by calculating Total Publication (TP) and Average Citation Per Paper (ACPP). The Journal of Academic Librarianship leads the list with the highest total publications, 19, having an H-index of 9 and a strong Cite Score (5.3), indicating its significant academic impact. Following closely, the Journal of Librarianship and Information Science, with 17 publications having an H-index of 8, also maintains a solid reputation with a Cite Score of 4.7. Library Management (16 publications) has a comparable H-index (8) but a lower Cite Score (2.7), suggesting a specialized readership. As it was discontinued from the Scopus list, Library Philosophy and Practice has a lower citation impact (Cite Score 0.4 till 2020). Public Library Quarterly (H-index 6, Cite Score 3.5) focuses on public library research, while the IFLA Journal (H-index 6, SNIP 1.230) reflects global engagement. College & Research Libraries News has a high average citation per paper (ACPP 10.62) but a lower overall Cite Score (0.8), indicating a niche influence. Library and Information Science Research, having a Cite Score of 4.6, maintains strong academic relevance despite fewer publications. Journal of Library Administration and College & Research Libraries round out the list, with the latter boasting the highest ACPP (24.66), showing its significant citation impact despite fewer publications. However, in the field of library Standards, these publications reflect a combination of worldwide reach, specialized research focus, and widespread academic influence.

Table 2: Top Relevant Source

Source	TP	ACPP	H – Index	Cite Score (2023)	SJR	SNIP
Journal of Academic Librarianship	19	16.42	9	5.3	0.858	1.668
Journal of librarianship and information science	17	10.82	8	4.7	0.625	1.413
Library management	16	11.81	8	2.7	0.606	0.959
Library philosophy and practice	13	3.18	3	0.4(2020)	0.233	0.224
Public library quarterly	13	7.30	6	3.5	0.703	1.189
IFLA journal	12	5.83	6	2.7	0.538	1.230
College and research libraries news	8	10.62	5	0.8	0.249	0.409
Library and information science research	8	2.75	3	4.6	0.696	1.429
Journal of Library Administration	7	3.14	3	2.7	0.702	1.045
College and research libraries	6	24.66	4	3.1	0.821	1.368

Important Authors of Publication Library Standards

The authorship patterns analysis of the documents from 1879 to 2024 (Table 3) reveals a significant shift from single-author publications to increased multi-authored collaborations. While single-author works (158) were more prevalent in earlier years, multi-authored publications (215) have progressively increased, particularly from the late 20th century onward. The overall degree of collaboration (DC) stands at 0.42, with a notable rise in recent years, exceeding 0.50 from the 2000s onward and reaching 0.81 in 2024. The data indicates a growing trend towards co-authorship, especially in the past two decades. The highest number of total publications was recorded in 2020 (31), followed by 2024 (27) and 2022 (26), further demonstrating a surge in collaborative research. In earlier years, DC values were often at 0.00, reflecting a prevalence of single-author publications, whereas recent years consistently show DC values above 0.65, emphasizing a shift toward teamwork in research. Some years, such as 1963, 1991, and 2001, have missing author data, affecting collaboration calculations. Generally, the

increasing degree of collaboration aligns with global academic trends, highlighting the growing importance of interdisciplinary research and cooperative knowledge production.

Table 3: Authorship pattern and Degree of Collaboration (1879-2024)

Year	Authorship Pattern					Total Publication	DC
	Single Author	Two authors	Three Authors	Four Authors	Five and above		
1879	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.00
1963	1	0	0	0	0	1*	0.00
1965	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.00
1966	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.00
1969	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.00
1978	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.00
1980	1	1	0	0	0	2	0.50
1981	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.00
1982	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.00
1983	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.00
1985	1	1	0	0	0	2	0.50
1986	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.00
1988	2	2	0	0	0	4	0.50
1989	2	1	0	0	0	3	0.33
1990	3	1	0	0	0	4	0.25
1991	0	0	0	0	0	0*	0.00
1992	1	0	1	0	0	2	0.50
1993	2	1	0	0	0	3	0.33
1995	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.00
1996	3	1	0	0	0	4	0.25
1997	2	1	0	0	0	3	0.33
1998	2	2	1	0	0	5	0.60
1999	2	1	1	0	0	4*	0.50
2000	3	0	0	0	0	3	0.00
2001	5	0	0	0	0	5*	0.00
2002	2	1	0	1	0	4	0.50
2003	3	1	0	0	0	4	0.33
2004	4	3	0	1	1	9	0.56
2005	1	1	0	0	1	3	0.66
2006	4	2	0	0	0	6*	0.33
2007	6	6	1	1	0	14	0.57
2008	4	0	0	1	0	5	0.20
2009	2	3	1	0	0	6	0.67
2010	4	7	3	0	0	14	0.71
2011	5	4	3	0	0	12	0.58
2012	4	3	0	0	1	8*	0.50

2013	2	6	3	1	0	12	0.83
2014	8	4	4	0	2	18	0.56
2015	9	4	2	0	0	15	0.40
2016	11	2	2	2	0	17	0.35
2017	8	4	2	1	1	16	0.50
2018	8	5	2	0	1	16	0.50
2019	3	6	2	1	0	12	0.75
2020	11	12	6	1	1	31	0.65
2021	5	12	5	1	1	24	0.79
2022	7	8	5	3	3	26	0.73
2023	3	7	4	3	2	19	0.84
2024	5	13	6	1	2	27	0.81
Total	158	126	55	18	16	373	0.42

*(No author found document is not counted)

The ratio of collaborative scientific articles in a specific subject to all scientific articles published over the same period is measured by the DC metric. The equation that Subramanyam proposed was used in this analysis (Subramanyam, 1983) as

$$\text{Degree of collaboration (DC)} = \frac{N_m}{N_s + N_m}$$

Whereas,

N_m = multi-authored publications

N_s = Single-authored publications

High Impact Cited Publications

Table 4 highlights the most cited academic library standards-related documents, with "Survey of Information Literacy Instructional Practices in U.S. Academic Libraries" by Julien, Gross, and Latham (2018) leading the list with 107 total citations and a high annual citation rate (TC per year) of 13.38. This pattern suggests resilient, ongoing significance in information literacy practices. Other notable works include "Best Practices for Online Video Tutorials" (2010) and "Academic Library Websites: Current Practice and Future Directions" (2006), indicating constant interest in digital instructional methods and web presence. Emerging trends, such as using chatbots in libraries (Susan McKie & Narayan, 2019), also show a significant impact, with 61 citations and a high TC per year of 8.71. Studies on bibliometric practices, research support services, and cloud computing further reflect evolving library roles. The presence of research from diverse regions, including Pakistan, underscores global contributions to academic library advancements. These citation trends reveal key focus areas in library science, particularly information literacy, digital engagement, and emerging technologies. We found that none of the

documents are directly linked to library standards, which highlights the demand for this type of research.

Table 4: High Impact Cited Publications

Document	Author/ Year	Total Citations	Total Citation per Year	Normalized TC
Survey of Information Literacy Instructional Practices in U.S. Academic Libraries	Heidi Julien, Melissa Gross & Don Latham (2018)	107	13.38	7.54
Best Practices for Online Video Tutorials: A Study of Student Preferences and Understanding	Melissa Bowles-Terry Follow, Merinda Hensley Lisa & Janicke Hinchliffe (2010)	74	4.63	5.21
Academic Library Web Sites: Current Practice and Future Directions	Brian Detlor & Vivian Lewis (2006)	65	3.25	6.07
Communities of Practice at an Academic Library: A New Approach to Mentoring at the University of Idaho	Kristin J. Henrich & Ramirose Attebury (2010)	64	4.00	4.50
Enhancing the Academic Library Experience with Chatbots: An Exploration of Research and Implications for Practice	Indra Ayu Susan Mckie & Bhuva Narayan (2019)	61	8.71	5.63
How implementation of bibliometric practice affects the role of academic libraries	Fredrik Åström & Joacim Hansson (2012)	56	4.31	3.59
“Making space” in practice and education: research support services in academic libraries	Mary Anne Kennan, Sheila Corral & Waseem Afzal (2019)	54	4.50	4.84
The impact of cloud computing on the future of academic library practices and services	Judith Mavodza (2013)	49	3.77	3.14
Internet Subject Guides in Academic Libraries: An Analysis of Contents, Practices, and Opinions	Rebecca Jackson & Lorraine J. Pellack(2004)	48	2.18	3.15
Current status of information literacy instruction practices in medical libraries of Pakistan	Midrar Ullah & Kanwal Ameen (2014)	42	3.50	3.76

Publication Contribution of Countries

The data reveals a strong dominance of the USA, with 338 occurrences, far surpassing all other countries, suggesting a significantly higher level of engagement, presence, or influence in the field. Nigeria, Canada, China, and Australia form a second tier, with frequencies in the 30s, while India and the UK follow closely with 25 occurrences each. The dataset reflects a miscellaneous global representation across multiple continents, yet notable differences exist, with countries like Brazil (9) showing lower engagement. This distribution suggests that North America and key regions in Asia and Europe play a leading role. At the same time, lower frequencies in other areas may indicate potential opportunities for increased outreach or participation.

Figure 2: The production of documents worldwide

Three-Field Plot

The three-field plot (Figure 3) illustrates the dynamic interconnections between authors' affiliated institutions (AU_UN), source journals (SO), and research descriptors (DE), providing a vision of the structure of scholarly communication in Library Standards. The visualization highlights that institutions such as Kwara State University, University of Nevada, and Lund University are prominent contributors to well-regarded journals like Library Management, Journal of Librarianship and Information Science, and Journal of Academic Librarianship. The United States emerges as a dominant actor, indicating its central role in shaping discourse across various themes. Frequently occurring descriptors such as academic libraries, public libraries,

training, COVID-19, cataloguing, and library services reveal key areas of ongoing research. Furthermore, the broad connections of institutions like the University of Nevada across multiple journals and topics underscore a diverse and engaged scholarly output. Emerging themes such as staff development and collaboration point toward shifting priorities and evolving needs in the profession, especially in response to global challenges and technological transformation.

Figure 3: Three-field plot of Affiliation, Source, and Keyword

Thematic Analysis

The thematic map illustrates the structure and development of research themes in the field, categorized across four quadrants based on centrality (relevance) and density (development). In (Fig.4), the top-right quadrant, motor themes such as "library, human, article" and "terminology, norm, health information" are both well-developed and highly applicable, representing that they are core, influential areas in the field. The top-left quadrant features niche but mature themes like "electronic publishing" and "e-book selection," which are specialized yet less connected to other themes. In contrast, the bottom-right quadrant contains basic themes like "libraries," "public libraries," and "academic libraries" that are central to the domain but are still developing in coherence. The bottom-left quadrant with niche themes highlights emerging or possibly declining topics such as "semi-structured interviews," "sustainable development," and "smart city," which are currently underdeveloped and peripheral. Overall, the map reveals a strong focus

on library and health information topics, with opportunities for growth in foundational library themes and sustainability-related research.

Fig 4: Thematic Analysis

Keywords and Network Analysis of Publications

Keywords in an article highlight the central themes of the topic and play a crucial role in understanding the focus of the research. As part of the analysis, published literature was examined to identify any missing or overlooked terms relevant to the subject. According to the VOSviewer manual, "Each link has a strength indicated by a positive numerical value. The higher this value, the stronger the link. The total link strength reflects the number of publications in which two keywords appear together" (Patel et al., 2021). In the present study, bibliographic data revealed a total of 1,196 keywords associated with the titles of the publications. To ensure relevance and clarity, a co-occurrence threshold of 3 was applied, resulting in the identification of 83 significant keywords using VOSviewer. The red cluster centers around "academic libraries," linking with terms like "cataloguing," "metadata," and "electronic resources," suggesting a focus on technical and organizational aspects of academic library systems. The green cluster highlights "public libraries" and their community-oriented roles, highlighting keywords such as "social media," "community involvement," and "guidelines." Blue and light blue clusters relate to "staff development," "accessibility," "health literacy," and "resilience," reflecting a recent shift in library services. Meanwhile, the purple and orange clusters involve

broader themes such as "library science," "curriculum," and "medical libraries," often tied to research and professional practice. The dimensions of each node indicate the frequency of the associated keywords, whereas the connecting lines illustrate the intensity of their co-occurrence. Overall, the network map expresses traditional and emerging research areas in library Standards, demonstrating interdisciplinary linkages and evolving priorities of digital Standards.

Figure 5: Authors keywords co-occurrence network visualisation

Discussion and Conclusions

The bibliometric analysis offers a broad view of the scholarly landscape surrounding library standards. Although it demonstrates a normal annual growth rate of 0.48%, a notable surge in scholarly output has been observed since the early 2000s, peaking in 2020 with 31 publications. This continuous increase reflects a growing academic interest in library standards, likely influenced by technological transformations, evolving information needs, and institutional policy shifts, which urges the demand for digital standards. The dataset shows a relatively increasing publication of literature, with an average document age of 13.1 years, which has a cumulative citation count exceeding 10,000.

In the context of collaboration, library standards reflect a significant increase in co-authorship, with the collaboration coefficient increasing from 0.25 during the 1990s to 0.81 by 2024. This pattern highlights the increasing interest in interdisciplinary and institutional partnerships in enriching library standards. However, the level of international collaboration remains comparatively low at 4.97%, indicating an area of emerging global perspectives. Prominent scholarly journals, including *The Journal of Academic Librarianship* and the *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, dominate the field with high citation metrics, indicating their supremacy in scholarly communication in this domain. A diverse range of document types is represented, yet scholarly articles remain the leading format, mirroring the conventional mode of information dissemination prevalent in academic environments. The thematic and factorial analyses further reveal a complex research framework. Central themes such as library services, health information systems, and the standardization of terminology have robustly developed.

On the other hand, emerging domains such as sustainable development, intelligent libraries, and digital leadership indicate potential ways for future inquiry. The thematic clustering indicates a vibrant field where traditional library issues exist, with ideal demands for digital transformation and societal challenges. Contributions at the national level show a considerable strength of research output originating from the United States, followed by Nigeria, Canada, and China. While this emphasizes the potential leadership role played by North America, it simultaneously highlights regional inequalities, thereby presenting opportunities for enhanced involvement and representation from historically backward nations.

So, we found that this study highlights various emerging fields where library standards research continues to adapt to recent technological, educational, and institutional demands. The increasing collaboration, thematic diversification, and growing scholarly output indicate that the field is poised for further expansion. Future efforts should aim to enhance international collaboration, integrate interdisciplinary approaches, and address global challenges to ensure the sustained relevance and impact of library standards in a rapidly changing information environment.

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